

Challenges and Response: How Covid-19 effect the Educational Activities in Schools(A Case study of Lower Dir Khyber Pakhtunkhwa)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 27, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 14, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Education, Institutions, Widespread Disease, Affect. Burning issue</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4540620</p>	<p><i>Education is one of the basic institutions which play a vital role in the operation and sustainability of a society. This piece of study focused on the variouseffects of Covid-19 oneducational activities and which strategies would be better to adopt for the sack to carry on educational activities. The global outbreak of coronavirus is conclusively attributed to the direct contacts and social interactions of individuals. Because of the fatal nature of the virus and man is the major host for the virus, scientists have intimidated people to practice social distancing so that the further spreading of the virus may be stopped. This paper aims to explore how covid-19 affects the education system along with the learning and teaching process in educational institutions of District Lower Dir, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in Pakistan. For this purpose, 08 potential respondents (school teachers) from various schools were purposively selected and their views were taken through in-depth interviews. It was found that all the curriculum activities in schools were badly affected by the pandemic of covid-19. The findings of the study suggested that strategic planning regarding SOPs in schools and e-learning can control the spreading of this pandemic.</i></p>

Introduction

The outbreak of covid-19 (Coronavirus) was triggered in December 2019 in Wuhan city in Hubei province of China and spread quickly all over the globe. This pandemic is caused by the virus SARS-CoV-2. It is commonly perceived that this pandemic has serious health and physical consequences on human lives, however, it has created enormous social and psychological distress in society. Besides, it has also negatively affected the social structure and social fabric of the society by potentially paralyzing the education, family, political and social sectors across the world. Similarly, it is generally believed that coronavirus has negatively affected the social structure of Pakistani society after a few incidents of natural and social disasters including the devastating earthquake of 2005, and the flash flood of 2010. Some people have the belief that the spread of Covid-19 is more serious and psychologically threatening than the social and political disaster of the infamous event of 9/11. It is radically changing contemporary life, penetrating its social, political and monetary dimensions (WHO, 2020).

The Covid-19 pandemic has raised great changes in the structure and function of schools around the world. As per UNESCO 2020 report, almost 1.5 billion students in 165 nations have their learning encounters upset by the crisis. Jaime Saavedra, Global Director for Education, portrays it as the "biggest concurrent stun to all instructive frameworks in the course of our lives" (World Bank 2020). More explicit to Early Childhood Education, this global wellbeing emergency has accelerated exceptional and sensational changes in the lives of youngsters and their families. Around the world, the Covid-19 has additionally pushed the youth schooling framework to the skirt of breakdown and activated driving youth associations to advocate for Covid-19 financial and social improvement to secure early instruction program. However, Medical exploration recommends that, carefully, Covid-19 is anything but a "kids' infection" because there are just scarcely any affirmed instances of the Covid-19 among youngsters who contract the sickness, the casualty rate has been extremely low (Spaull, 2020). However, when we think about all parts of little youngsters' turn of events, the significant ramifications of the worldwide pandemic are apparent. The COVID-19 pandemic influences everybody and all over. It has been intensifying prior disparities, uncovering weaknesses in social, political and financial frameworks which are thus enhancing the deep-rooted effects of the pandemic. Based on the latest available data, over 93 million pre-primary students in 34 countries and 4.4 million pre-primary teachers (85 percent of whom are women) in 24 countries in the Asia Pacific regions are affected by COVID-19. However, it is expected to be most damaging for children in the poorest countries and those in already disadvantaged or having vulnerable situations. Youngsters are intrinsically defenseless because they rely upon grown-ups to have their most essential requirements met. At the point when those grown-ups come up short on the fortitude to adapt to the prompt, earnest, and different versatile requests a pandemic puts on families and when emotionally supportive networks don't exist, flounder, or stop, it can bring about unmitigated catastrophe for the extremely youthful. The most

affected “are those individuals routinely disadvantaged by the social injustice created by the misdistribution of power, money, and resources”. Especially for youngsters who are living in neediness, persistently sick, have disabilities, experience lodging, and food uncertainty, live in distant regions are underestimated by standard society (e.g., indigenous individuals and travelerlaborers) are experiencing disregard or misuse, issues are exacerbated by pandemics.

Since March 16, when the administration of Pakistan forced a countrywide lockdown to contain the spread of the infection, around 46 million school kids have been compelled to remain at home, notwithstanding the nation’s of now 22 million out-of-younger students. The overflow impacts of the monetary downturn incited by the episode have additionally compounded the circumstance by debilitating Pakistan's schooling framework, particularly as advancement subsidizing has been sliced at the public and common levels. In the nation where interest in the public area is now pitiful, COVID-19 has brought on additional "shrinkage" in assets accessible for the schooling framework conveyance. Coronavirus is set to amplify disparities in the training arrangement of Pakistan and is probably going to provoke an ascent in school dropout rates, subsequently expanding the quantity of out-of-younger students, particularly young ladies. With a financial downturn and rising joblessness, families will give an inclination to sending young men back to schools instead of young ladies, particularly in rustic and per-metropolitan regions (Clark et al., 2020).

The potential learning misfortunes acquired by youngsters and youths because of the pandemic are difficult to comprehend as the circumstance is as yet advancing, notwithstanding, while most non-public schools are offering separation learning through different computerized innovation stages, Pakistani kids in the nation's distant territories are lopsidedly distraught because of an absence of admittance to PCs or the web. The more extended their schools stay shut, the more troublesome it will be for these effectively weak youngsters to make up for lost time with learning (Crawford and et al, 2020).

The Rationale of the study

Coronavirus not just suspended ordinary youth exercises and their activities, for example, going to schools, take classes, collaborating with more distant family and companions, playing outside, and investigating nature yet also, upset the resulting socio-enthusiastic advantages that build from kids' commitment in these encounters. The COVID-19 Pandemic has brought about great devastation in Pakistan with a specialfocus on children from the age group of 10-16 years in Middle and High-level classes in schools. The studyillustrates an in-depth analysis of the current pandemic conditions and theirimpact on the children’s educational system. The study discusses the problems faced by schoolchildren duringLockdown in terms of learning and teachingaspects.

Objective and Research Questionof the study

1. To find out the impact of Covid-19 on the educational activities i.e. learning and teaching process at various schools in the targeted area.
2. How the pandemic affectsthe learning and teaching processin schools?

Material and Methods

The study focuses on Middle and High-level schools of District Lower Dir, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, from the age group of 10-16 years who are studying from 6th standard to 10th standard. There are 20 schools including Government and Private Institutions out of which private schools are around 8 and Government schools are 12 in the targeted area. Through the Random Sampling lottery method, the researcher chooses4 schools from Private institutions and 6 Government schools to obtain the feasibility of the study. So, out of 10 schools (School name not revealed for confidentiality purpose), nearly 1080 students are therein private schools and 1610 students are in Government schools. Owing the Qualitative nature of the inquiry, 08 respondents (4 school teachers from each category) are chosen through a purposive sampling methodwere interviewed. Moreover, 08 students (4 students from each category) were selected for data collection purpose. The information was broken down by translating the information and distinguishing proof of topics for understanding, the topical investigation offers accentuation to inspecting, pinpointing, and designs from the information (Creswell, 2010). These themes in the information were noteworthy to the clarification of the reality associated with the research questions. Individual perception and past writing were additionally remembered for the subjective information investigation to comprehend the perspectives of the respondents.

Result and Discussion

Effect on Academic Interaction

Systematic education is very important for all. It facilitates quality learning all through life among people of any age group, caste, creed, religion and region. It is the process of achieving knowledge, values, skills, beliefs and moral habits. The outbreaks of Covid-19 create obstacles in the way of educational activities ranging from learning to examination. Particularly, the activities of learning, reading, interacting and examination are highly affected due to this pandemic. The issue is not confined to any aspect of society but, the education system which is the key to the dynamism and progress of society is highly affected. One of the respondents expressed:

“The level of interaction did not remain the same between the students and teachers in school. Both teachers and students followed SOPs in school to protect themselves from the widespread of Covid-19”.

It means that interaction and learning through social contact is very important in this whole process. Both segments try their level best to protect the widespread coronavirus and escape from this pandemic. This kind of interaction badly affects the learning process in school. The above statement also reflects that proper interaction between students and teachers produces a hurdle in the way of learning and reading.

Education is one of the basic institutions of society. It plays vital part in socialization and culture transmission to the next generation. One of the respondents exposed:

“This pandemic of covid-19 caused a bad impression on the overall educational development and progress. The schools, colleges, and universities throughout the country are closed which badly affects the grooming of students in the future. It means that hurdles are created in the way to achieve our educational goals for this educational year”.

This issue is very crucial because the development of a nation is measure with the parameter of educational qualities. The people are unwilling to send their children to school in this critical situation. Everybody is afraid in this regard to escape themselves as much more as possible. McCormack et al. (1997) find out that education is key to the progress and betterment of society. Also, they highlighted that education imparts the upcoming generation to combat the difficulties and obstacles faced by people and society. In such away one of the respondents highlighted:

“The educational institutions provide an opportunity to learn by imitation. The students copy their teachers whatever action they performed. The students try to exercise all these actions and behaviors in their day to day activities. The fear of Covid-19 keeps the student away from the learning of imitation and intimate interaction”.

The aforesaid statement depicted that close interaction between teachers and students is very important for the overall learning process. Some student likes to learn by imitation and copy the teacher action and behavior in class. This statement support and validate the findings of Jan et al. (2020) that learning and teaching are both affected by the outbreak of this pandemic. So, all the learning activities are disturbed due to the outbreak of Covid-19. One of the respondents revealed that:

“Most of the students feel uncomfortable being at home all the time as it restricts their ideas, feelings, thoughts and emotions. The environment after the reopening of schools have not remained the same. Fear about the spread of Coronavirus and strictly following the SOPs creates a distance in the teaching and learning process”.

The statement explores that students in schools are not comfortable. A comfortable environment plays a vital role in the whole process of learning and teaching. Owing to the curse of this pandemic students are unable to develop their ideas and feeling in a free environment because students are restricted and confined in school.

Effect on Teaching

The overall conclusion of schools due to the Covid-19 pandemic is exceptional, influencing more than 1.5 billion youngsters, as per a United Nations strategy. In nations like Pakistan, the circumstance represents a high danger of understudies, particularly young ladies, exiting and not getting back to schools when instructive organizations at long last resume. Teaching is the fundamental domain of the learning process. This is an undeniable fact that the whole process of learning, teaching, and remembering process is affected by the recent pandemic of Covid-19. The environment of school has not remained the same as it was before of this pandemic. Each and everybody is in suspense and likes to avoided contact and interaction with colleagues in educational institutions.

Teachers who are skilled in communication, classroom management, and appropriate discipline techniques create a positive learning environment. Although being well versed in your subject area is important, being able to communicate necessary skills and concepts in a way students can understand is crucial. The activities of teaching consist of interaction between students and teachers, critical thinking, production, reflection and problem-solving. One of the aspirants disclosed;

“Teaching is a very important aspect in the whole educational process and this epidemic highly scratches this section of learning. Also, he added that teaching about instructions for learners and can guide them towards their achievements.”

The above-mentioned statement means that Covid-19 not only cuts the learning activities of students but teaching also infected. Teaching is regarded as one of the fundamental elements of educational activities. The activities of teaching like interaction, reflection and production segments are affected due to the coronavirus. One of the respondents revealed:

“That continuity in teaching is closed and due to this reason, the environment of educational institutions is suffered. The consistency in teaching is a major variable in which the teachers learn something new on daily basis. Now the teachers are unable to have access to all these processes that is why the teaching in educational institutions are influenced due to Covid-19”.

Added by another respondent:

“The levels of interaction among the teachers in educational institutions are low due to the recent epidemic of coronavirus. This is a fact that will affect the quality of teaching in schools because teachers are also learning from each other. So, we can say that overall the learning process in educational institutes are suffered due to Covid-19”.

Education is the privilege of each youngster and is the bedrock of an equitable society. Pakistan has a portion of the world's most noticeably terrible training markers with 40% of youngsters not going to any type of formal schooling. The COVID-19 emergency has additionally bothered the circumstance. The time has come to ask what estimates the government needs to make the instruction area more manageable, impartial, comprehensive, and tough despite the emergency.

Examination Section

The examination section is a key and vital variable in the learning process. At present, three types of examination systems are being used in Pakistan i. e semester without external evaluation, semester with external evaluation, and annual with external evaluation. A good examination system whether annual or semester indicates what is taught and how it is taught. Assessment of educational outcome is most important in respect that how more students get the goal of the lesson. Asking students to demonstrate their understanding of the subject matter is critical to the learning process; it is essential to evaluate whether the educational goals and standards of the lessons are being met. One of the respondents exposed:

“The system of examination in Pakistan also suffered due to Covid-19. The outbreaks of this pandemics and smart lockdown restricted students at homes. The students unable to appeared in exams”.

Another aspirant explore in the same way;

Provincial instruction offices are taking a shot at correction of curricular objectives for the year to make them more practical, with an exhortation from subject specialists. Therapeutic guidance methodologies, demonstrated to be powerful, can be joined with justified objectives to guarantee all kids, especially those prohibited from instructional help during school terminations, can get up to speed. At last, this crisis presents an occasion to test methodologies that permit showing youngsters at the correct level, rather than prescribed student learning objectives (SLOs).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that the whole setup of schools was closed from the outbreaks of Covid-19. In the imposed lockdown, students were confined to their homes, and all the educational activities were suffered. The findings of the study disclosed that overall educational interaction between students and teachers is confined, the activities of learning, examination and other co-curricular activities are also restricted in schools. The study recommended that to keep physical distance in classrooms, establish e-learning and e-exam for students and avoid gathering in recreational and sports activities in school. Also, the study suggested that government/school administration urged to follow the precautionary measure to protect the students from the pandemic and to continue the educational activities.

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